

Enhancing Caregiver Practices in Pediatric and Adolescent Antibiotic Use through Educational Posters: Cross Sectional Study**Mutyalwar Piyush¹, Bhagwat Nikhil², Salame Rohit³, Falke Bhalchandra⁴, Avinash Tekade⁵**¹Junior Resident, Dept. of Physiology, Department of Physiology, GMC, Chandrapur²Assistant Professor, Department of Pediatrics, GMC, Chandrapur³Associate Professor, Department of Medicine, GMC, Chandrapur⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Medicine, GMC, Chandrapur⁵Professor, Department of Physiology, GMC Chandrapur and Dean GMC, Gadchiroli

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Abstract:

Background: Respiratory infections are prevalent among children, and antibiotics, particularly in suspension form, are commonly prescribed to manage bacterial infections. Proper use of these suspensions, including accurate reconstitution, administration, and storage, is crucial to their effectiveness. The study focuses on addressing these issues to educate caregivers and improve practices through the use of visual educational tools. To Evaluate the impact of educational posters on improving caregivers' knowledge and practices related to the handling of pediatric and adolescent antibiotic suspensions and promote accurate and safe handling of these medications through visual aids. This is a prospective, interventional study done in September and October 2024 which was conducted in pediatric clinic where caregivers frequently visit to receive prescriptions and medications for children. The study followed a pre-test and post-test design to measure changes in knowledge and practices. In the pre-education assessment, caregivers demonstrated strong knowledge in specific areas, with 92.54% knowing the correct amount of water for reconstitution, 93.42% aware of the need to shake the bottle after reconstitution, and 80.7% understanding proper storage for diluted medicine. However, significant gaps were noted, such as only 10.96% knowing the effective duration of reconstituted antibiotics and 24.12% understanding preparatory steps like loosening the powder before reconstitution. After the educational intervention, caregivers achieved a 100% correct response rate. Hence, we conclude study highlighted a mix of strong and weak areas in caregivers' knowledge and practices regarding antibiotic administration for children. While most participants were well-versed in core aspects, there were critical gaps, particularly around preparatory steps and the timing of reconstituted antibiotics. Educational posters proved to be an effective tool for bridging these gaps, resulting in a substantial improvement in adherence to correct practices. The findings emphasize the need for clear, visual, and easy-to-understand educational materials, tailored to caregivers' demographics, especially targeting younger parents who are the primary caregivers. Future educational strategies should leverage visual aids and communication platforms that resonate with the target audience, ensuring proper medication use and reducing the risk of errors.

Keywords: Antibiotic Handling, Pediatric Care, Educational Intervention, Reconstitution of Antibiotics, Caregiver Practices, Antibiotic Resistance.

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Introduction

Respiratory infections are one of the most common diseases affecting children, and primary-care pediatricians typically manage the majority of cases in outpatient settings [1]. When infection is caused by bacteria then antibiotic is the drug of choice, most of newborns, infants, and preschool children receive antibiotic in the form of dry powder for reconstitution to suspension before administration [2]. Antibiotics prescribed for infants and young children are usually dispensed as oral suspensions because of children's inability to swallow tablets or

capsules, unavailability of certain antibiotics in a chewable tablet form and the discomfort, expense, and associated risk of antibiotic injections [3]. The most common reasons for antibiotic prescription in children are Streptococcal pharyngitis, community-acquired pneumonia, sinusitis, and acute otitis media [4].

Fever is a well-established sign of illness, yet it can trigger fear and anxiety in both parents and healthcare providers [5]. Amoxicillin plus clavulanic acid has been identified as the most

commonly prescribed pediatric antibiotic in primary care settings, consistent with findings from similar studies [6]. Antibiotics are misused because many patients do not take them according to their doctor or pharmacist instructions. They may stop taking their antibiotics too soon before their illness is completely cured. Some patients save unused medicine and take it later for another illness or pass it to other ill family members or friends and some patients go to the pharmacy and take antibiotics as an over-the-counter drug [7].

Appropriate use of suspensions involves correct reconstitution, appropriate concentration, accurate dose administration, adherence to the recommended duration of treatment, and proper storage conditions [8].

Bottles of oversized oral antibiotic suspensions had been filled up with water to nearly their full volumes, which reduced the concentration of active substances to half or less and may threaten the treatment outcome. This problem is not confined to any particular country but can arise in any situation where non-healthcare professionals reconstitute pediatric oral suspensions using oversized bottles [9].

Most medications, as indicated in the following sections, have strict temperature ranges at which they should be maintained to assure their potency. Other factors, including light, humidity, and packaging, also influence the shelf life and sterility of a drug. Strong packaging is critical; if a parenteral drug (packaged in a syringe for ready use) is frozen, the drug may be fully potent, but its sterility may have been lost due to hairline cracks in the plastic caused by freezing. Polyvinyl (plastic) containers often used to package drugs may affect product stability. Glass containers, although considered the most inert of storage vessels, may leach alkali and associated decomposition products into the product, thereby initiating chemical reactions that alter drug potency. The inclusion of preservatives in the drug formulation and the actual processes used by the manufacturer may also make products more or less resilient in the face of prolonged storage. Thus, for most of the drug products listed, stability and sterility cannot be guaranteed if products are stored under conditions deviating from those recommended by the manufacturer [10]. Improper storage of medicines is frequent, but the size of the problem has not previously been investigated or whether it is possible to save money by continuing to use improperly stored drugs [11].

As childhood medicinal drug overdose is one of the major public health issues worldwide, health workers including prescribers and dispensers must provide necessary individualized instructions to raise knowledge about antibiotic suspension usage and to implement appropriate practices [12].

Overprescription or the use of incorrect doses that are reported at higher prevalence in developing countries nurtures antibiotic resistance [13]. Oral liquid medications usually come with a dose delivery device such as medication cups, droppers, calibrated spoons, and syringes [14]. Household spoons should not be used for delivery of medications as they are not accurate. In fact, these spoons are usually available in different sizes. Syringes have many advantages; they are accurate even for small volumes, they are easy to use and to be cleaned. Regarding dosing cups dosing error are common with them, so as a general rule they should not be used for doses less than 5 ml even if the cup has calibration less than 5 ml [15].

Small font size and low contrast on medication labels can make it challenging for caregivers, particularly the elderly, to read and understand essential information. This may lead to errors in reconstitution, incorrect dilution, or improper storage, potentially reducing the effectiveness of the medication. Difficulty in interpreting instructions can result in inaccurate preparation of antibiotic suspensions, leading to improper dosing and affecting therapeutic outcomes. Unclear storage guidelines may cause caregivers to store medications at incorrect temperatures, compromising drug stability and potency. Inconsistencies in labelling across product variants can further confuse caregivers, increasing the risk of errors. Addressing these issues requires collaboration between pharmaceutical companies, regulators, and healthcare providers to create accessible, standardized, and user-friendly medication instructions. Clear visuals, larger fonts, and consistent labelling practices can help improve accuracy and enhance patient safety.

Hence, we have undertaken present study to evaluate the impact of educational posters on improving caregivers' knowledge and practices related to the reconstitution, administration, and storage of antibiotic suspensions in pediatric care. Also to promote accurate and safe handling of antibiotic suspensions through visual educational tools. These objectives aim to assess the role of visual aids, like posters, in improving practical knowledge and reducing errors in the use of antibiotic suspensions for children.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: This is a prospective, interventional study conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of an educational poster on improving caregivers' practices related to the reconstitution, administration, and storage of antibiotic suspensions in pediatric patients done in September and October 2024.

The study followed a pre-test and post-test design to measure changes in knowledge and practices.

The study was conducted in pediatric clinic and hospitals where caregivers frequently visit to receive prescriptions and medications for children.

Study Population: Caregivers of pediatric patients who dilute, administer and storage the antibiotic suspensions.

Inclusion Criteria

- Caregivers who are responsible for preparing and administering antibiotic suspensions to children.
- To keep the uniformity of study only those who were prescribed Syp Amoxicillin plus Clavulanic acid was included in the study as it was most common antibiotic prescribed.
- Willingness to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Caregivers who are healthcare professionals with advanced knowledge of medication administration.
- Those who are not involved in preparing or administering the antibiotic suspensions.

Sample Size: A sample size of 228 was calculated using a power analysis with $\alpha = 0.05$, 80% power, and a moderate effect size ($d = 0.5$). This accounts for a 10% dropout rate and ensures statistical validity, consistent with prior studies on educational intervention

Educational Poster

Used for present study as: A bilingual poster (English and Marathi) with visual aids and diagrams illustrating the correct steps for reconstitution,

administration, and storage of antibiotic suspensions.[16]

Questionnaire: A validated 12-question survey assessed caregivers' knowledge and practices pre- and post-intervention.[17] Reviewed by six pharmacy experts, it achieved a content validity score of 0.94.[18]

- **Baseline Assessment:** Administered a questionnaire to assess caregivers' knowledge and identify gaps.
- **Intervention:** Displayed an educational poster in high-traffic areas, with staff reinforcing its content.
- **Post-Intervention Assessment:** Re-administered the questionnaire to evaluate knowledge changes.
- **Data Collection:** Compiled and analyzed pre- and post-intervention responses.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical clearance was granted by the Institutional Ethics Committee of GMC Chandrapur. Confidentiality was maintained, and written informed consent in the local language was obtained from parents or guardians after explaining the study.

Results

Age and Sex of Patients: Table 1 suggest Maximum patients seeking healthcare and where desired antibiotic was prescribed was above 12 years with 23.68%(n=54) and least from 3-6 year old group with 18.85% (n=43).

Age of patients	Number	Percentage
0-3 yrs	45	19.73%
3-6 yrs	43	18.85%
6-9 yrs	49	21.49%
9-12 yrs	47	20.61%
> 12 yrs	54	23.68%

Males were 53.63% (n=120) and females were 47.37% (n=108) who took treatment according to Table 2

Sex of caregivers	Number	Percentage
Male	120	52.63%
Female	108	47.37%

Age group, Education and Relationship of Caregiver: Table 3 suggests that the majority of caregivers are in the 20-30 years age group, making

up 61.4% of the total caregivers, while only a small proportion (3.5%) are above 60 years old.

Age	Number	Percentage
20-30 years	139	60.96%
30-40 years	41	17.98%
40-50 years	23	10.08%
50-60 years	16	70.17%
>60 years	9	3.94%

Table 4 suggest that most of the caregiver were HSC passed with 31.57% (n=72) and just 12.28% (n= 28) were educated below SSC.

Education	Number	Percentage
< SSC	28	12.28%
SSC	62	27.19%
HSC	72	31.57%
Graduate	64	28.07%

Table 5 suggest that mother was most common caregiver with 88 %.

Relation	Number	Percentage
Mother	202	88.59%
Father	14	6.14%
Grandmother	10	4.38%
Others	2	0.87%

A chi-square test was conducted to evaluate the distribution of correct and wrong responses across

various aspects of antibiotic preparation and administration. The results are summarized in Table 6

Question	Correct answer Percentage	Wrong Answer Percentage	Chi-square (χ^2)	p-value	Interpretation
Checked expiry date	70.17%	29.82%	3.60	0.058	Not significant
Storage of medicine	61.40%	38.59%	9.26	0.002	Significant
Water for reconstitution	88.15%	11.80%	107.51	3.45×10^{-25}	Highly significant
Shake bottle to loosen powder	24.12%	75.87%	61.07	5.51×10^{-15}	Highly significant
Quantity of water to mix	92.54%	7.45%	148.48	3.73×10^{-34}	Highly significant
Shake again after reconstitution	93.42%	6.57%	157.23	4.57×10^{-36}	Highly significant
Time duration after mixing	10.96%	89.03%	138.96	4.48×10^{-32}	Highly significant
Storage of diluted medicine	80.70%	19.29%	85.96	1.83×10^{-20}	Highly significant
Interval of dosing	56.14%	43.85%	3.44	0.064	Not significant
Shake bottle every time before use	93.42%	6.57%	157.23	4.57×10^{-36}	Highly significant
Measurement to give drug	86.84%	13.15%	96.18	1.05×10^{-22}	Highly significant
Use of reconstituted drug	81.57%	18.42%	90.95	1.48×10^{-21}	Highly significant

Discussion

Education Material: Usually, package inserts are the most important and the only source of information for patients and their caregivers regarding the safety and proper administration of drugs. However, the drug inserts have been reported to lack important drug information in Europe and the USA [26]. Most of the manufacturers of reputed

company gives instructions on the on the label provided with the medicine. But it seemed very difficult to read it with naked eyes. Font used on the label was too small and photo clarity was also not good. Though instructions were given on double strength drugs most of the companies didn't provide any pictorial info on single strength drug.

(Fig 1):

Houts, P. S., et al. discusses how visuals improve health communication, understanding, and adherence, which is often more achievable with posters than small text labels [27]. Kripalani, S. et al. examines challenges with medication labels and highlights the benefit of more visual, clear communication strategies to improve adherence [28].

Language barrier also have impact on understanding the instruction on label as most of reputed company mention instruction only in English and are of small size.

According to Zu et al the educational sheets alone were less effective than in-person pharmacist education but were more effective than the package inserts in our study [17]. But Mousavi Jazayeri et al findings were different in a study on patient education, it was found that visual aids, including posters, improved patient understanding and compliance with medication instructions. Visual cues help bridge communication gaps, especially in busy or noisy environments where verbal instructions may not be clearly understood [26]. Also, Morrow, D. et al emphasized that visual aids improve the comprehension of health information, especially for patients with low literacy. Posters that use images, symbols, and easy-to-read text can significantly enhance understanding compared to verbal instructions alone [27].

Demographics of Patient

Table 1 and Table 2 shows that there was no significant difference in age group of the children along with gender who took treatment.

Demographics of Caregiver

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Age group of Caregiver: The data from Table 3 suggests: that younger adults (20-30 years) are primarily responsible for administering antibiotics, likely due to typical family structures with young parents as caregivers. Educational interventions should target this group, utilizing digital platforms or social media. The small percentage (3.50%) of caregivers aged over 60 are less involved in administering antibiotics, highlighting the need for clear, accessible instructions for all age groups.

Education of Caregiver: Table 4 suggests most caregivers (87.72%) have at least secondary education. However, the presence of caregivers with lower education levels suggests the need for simple, clear instructions. Pictorial presentations can help make the information accessible and understandable to individuals with varying educational backgrounds.

Relationship with Caregiver

Table 5 shows that mothers are the primary caregivers in 88.59% of cases, followed by fathers (6.14%) and grandmothers (4.38%), with the "Others" category (0.87%) including other relatives or caregivers. This reinforces the central role of mothers in children's healthcare and suggests that educational interventions aimed at mothers could enhance medication adherence and understanding.

Knowledge of Reconstitution, Administration, and storage of Oral Antibiotics before Education

Checked instructions before use

In our study, 160 (70%) of 228 caregivers reported reading all instructions, including the expiry date, before administering the medication. A study by Al

Rahmani et al. found that 347 (86.8%) of 400 mothers read the instructions on the box or package insert, and 311 (77.8%) understood them.[19] Similarly, a previous study showed that 100 (45%) of 222 consumers always read the information on the drug package leaflet.[8]

Storage of medicine in form of dry powder

In our study, 140 (61%) caregivers correctly stored dry powder antibiotics below 25°C, demonstrating good knowledge of storage practices which is higher than the 44.2% of mothers in Al Rahmani et al.'s study who stored dry powder antibiotics in a medicinal cabinet, with around half following the correct practice.[19] These findings are similar to a Palestinian study, where 40.6% of drugs were stored in a pharmacy cabinet.[17]

How do you use water for reconstitution?

In our study, 201 (88.15%) caregivers used sterile water or boiled and cooled water to reconstitute the dry powder. A study in Sri Lanka found that 779 out of 820 (95.0%) caregivers used boiled and cooled water correctly.[20] Similarly, a Palestinian study showed that 302 (75.5%) mothers used boiled and cooled tap water, while 7 (1.8%) used distilled water, which is also a correct practice.

Do you shake bottle to loose powder?

In our study, only 55 (24.12%) caregivers knew the importance of loosening the dry powder before adding water, ensuring even mixing and preventing clumping that could impair correct dosing. Kumarasinghe et al. observed suboptimal performance in 53.7% of caregivers during this critical step of the reconstitution process.[20] Proper loosening of the powder increases surface area, making reconstitution more efficient and reducing the need for excessive shaking.[27]

How much water do you mix?

In our study, 211 (93%) caregivers correctly understood the required amount of water to mix with the antibiotic powder for proper reconstitution, ensuring the correct concentration and consistency of the suspension. This finding aligns with a study by Al Rahmani et al., where 344 (86.6%) mothers followed the correct practice. However, in the study by Zyoud et al., 3.5% of participants did not believe the quantity of water should be specific, and 10.1% were uncertain. Similarly, Kumarasinghe et al. found that 59% of caregivers correctly filled the bottle to the indicated line. These results highlight a consistent level of knowledge about reconstitution practices across different studies.

Do you shake again after reconstitution?

In our study, 213 (93.42%) caregivers correctly shook the bottle again after reconstitution to ensure an even suspension, which is essential for accurate

dosing. This practice was more frequently followed compared to a study in Sri Lanka, where only 605 (73.8%) caregivers adhered to the same step. Shaking after reconstitution ensures that the antibiotic particles are evenly distributed, preventing uneven dosing and improving the medication's effectiveness. This highlights the importance of reinforcing such key practices to ensure optimal drug administration.

After how much time do you administer medicine after mixing?

In our study, only 25 (11%) caregivers were aware of the recommended 15-minute settling time after shaking the reconstituted antibiotic. This step is essential for ensuring the complete dissolution and even distribution of the active ingredient, improving dosing accuracy and the overall quality of the suspension. The process also allows air bubbles to dissipate and enhances the medication's taste and texture, making it more palatable for children. The low awareness of this practice highlights a need for further education to improve caregiver knowledge and ensure optimal antibiotic administration.

Where do you keep bottle after reconstitution?

Correct storage of reconstituted antibiotics, typically in a refrigerator, is essential to maintain their stability, effectiveness, and safety. Refrigeration prevents degradation and inhibits the growth of harmful bacteria or fungi. In our study, 184 (81%) caregivers correctly stored antibiotics in the refrigerator. This is higher compared to Al Rahmani et al.'s study, where 226 (56.5%) stored the suspension in the refrigerator, and Zyoud et al.'s study, where 70% stored antibiotics outside the fridge. These findings emphasize the importance of educating caregivers on proper storage practices.

How much interval do you keep while dosing?

Maintaining the correct dosing interval for oral antibiotics is crucial for effective treatment, preventing resistance, and ensuring the complete eradication of infections. It helps maintain optimal drug levels, minimizes side effects, and prevents bacteria from developing resistance. In our study, only 128 (56%) caregivers followed the correct practice of adhering to the dosing interval. Similarly, in Al Rahmani et al.'s study, 224 (56%) mothers incorrectly assumed that "three times daily" meant administering the medication with major meals, whereas the correct practice is to give the medication every 8 hours. This highlights the need for further education on proper dosing intervals.

Do you mix shake bottle every time before use?

Shaking the bottle before administering an oral antibiotic is essential to ensure that the active ingredients are evenly mixed, preventing underdosing or overdosing. In our study, 213 (93%)

caregivers correctly followed the practice of shaking the bottle before each use. Similarly, the study by Al Rahmani et al. reported that most mothers (392, 98%) also shook the drug bottle before use, highlighting the consistency of this important practice across different settings.

Which measurement do you use to give drug?

Correctly measuring the dose of an oral antibiotic is crucial for therapeutic effectiveness, preventing resistance, avoiding overdose, and maintaining consistent drug levels. In our study, 198 (87%) caregivers used a measuring spoon or cap, indicating good knowledge of proper dosing. However, 30 caregivers still used household spoons, which can lead to inaccurate dosing. In the study by Al Rahmani et al., 313 (78.2%) mothers preferred using a syringe for accurate dose administration, while 57 (14.3%) considered a household teaspoonful accurate. Overall, most mothers in both studies followed the correct dosing practice.

In How many days do you reconstituted drug?

The guideline to use reconstituted antibiotics within 7 days ensures drug stability, safety, and effectiveness, preventing degradation or contamination. In our study, 181 (82%) caregivers adhered to this guideline. Similarly, 394 (98.5%) mothers in the study by Al Rahmani et al. followed the recommended practice of using the antibiotic within 7 days. However, regarding the use of leftover suspensions, 26 (6.5%) mothers in Al Rahmani et al.'s study reused leftover antibiotics, which highlights an area of concern for proper medication handling.

The chi-square analysis revealed key findings:

1. Caregivers were well-informed about shaking the bottle, using the correct water amount, and storing diluted medicine (e.g., "Shake again after reconstitution" had a χ^2 of 157.23, $p < 0.001$).
2. Gaps in knowledge were found in "Time duration after mixing" ($\chi^2 = 138.96$, $p < 0.001$) and "Shake bottle to loosen powder" ($\chi^2 = 61.07$, $p < 0.001$).
3. Questions about "Checked instructions" ($p = 0.058$) and "Interval of dosing" ($p = 0.064$) showed no significant differences, suggesting uneven understanding.

The significant p-values for most of the questions suggest that while caregivers are knowledgeable about several key aspects of antibiotic preparation, there remain critical gaps that need to be addressed. Educational interventions should focus on improving understanding in areas where incorrect responses were more frequent, such as correct intervals of dosing and actions to take after mixing.

Role of Educational Poster in improving above problem

WHO guidelines highlight the importance of proper communication and education on hand hygiene and infection control, which is related to the handling and preparation of antibiotics. Effective education can reduce errors and improve outcomes [21]. CDC provides educational materials on proper antibiotic use, emphasizing the importance of caregivers understanding the correct administration, dilution, and storage of antibiotics to prevent misuse and resistance [22]. Morrison, A et al review article discusses the significance of patient education in improving medication adherence, highlighting how effective communication can help caregivers understand and follow proper medication protocols. [23]. Jha, N et al explores the consequences of improper antibiotic use and the role of education in ensuring proper administration. It emphasizes the importance of clear instructions to caregivers to avoid medication errors [24].

Conclusion

This study significantly enhances the handling, administration, and storage of pediatric antibiotics by addressing knowledge gaps and demonstrating the effectiveness of educational interventions. It identifies key areas of caregiver misunderstanding, such as the proper duration for reconstituted antibiotics' effectiveness and preparatory steps like loosening powder before reconstitution. The study shows how visual educational tools, like posters, can substantially improve caregiver knowledge, achieving a 100% correct response rate in post-intervention assessments.

Education addresses practical challenges such as miscommunication and improper storage, which can compromise treatment and contribute to resistance. By empowering caregivers, particularly young mothers, with accessible and visually engaging educational materials, the study strengthens their role in ensuring proper medication practices.

This research highlights the potential of simple, targeted educational interventions to promote better healthcare practices, reduce medication errors, and improve therapeutic outcomes. Its findings can guide the development of scalable, user-friendly educational strategies that may influence policies and practices in similar healthcare settings.

Limitations

1. Self-Reported Data.
2. Potential Recall Bias
3. Lack of Observational Data: References

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